

Spatial beam freezing in a few-mode optical fiber

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Abstract: We demonstrate a transition from positive to negative temperature of optical gas revealed by inversion of modal distribution as a power of femtosecond pulse carried by the fundamental fiber mode approaches a highly nonlinear regime. © 2025 The Author(s)

Nonlinear effects in multimode fibers have been studied extensively during the last two decades. This attention is driven by promising applications that surpass the use of singlemode fibers, as well as the possibility to study complex intermodal phenomena from the fundamental point of view. A recently introduced thermodynamic approach compares light propagation in multimode optical systems to a gas of photons trapped in a finite volume [1]. The weakly nonlinear dynamics of this photon gas is governed by the momentum exchange among photons, which may interact via their collisions. This permits us to define an optical temperature T and an optical chemical potential μ , which determine the mode power distribution at thermal equilibrium: the Rayleigh-Jeans law. Surprisingly, optical temperatures may have both positive and negative absolute values [2, 3]. In multimode optical fibers, for $T > 0$ the fundamental mode is the most populated; whereas for $T < 0$ the highest-order mode has the largest occupancy. At $T = \pm\infty$, the power is evenly distributed among all fiber modes. Wave thermalization in the weakly nonlinear regime at positive, near-zero temperatures describes the beam self-cleaning effect, which is observed in highly multimode optical fibers: the fundamental mode dominates the mode power distribution, and the beam at the fiber output exhibits a bell-shaped profile, with a corresponding relatively high spatial quality [4].

Here we consider a different situation, where the nonlinear contribution to the beam dynamics becomes relatively strong. From a thermodynamic perspective, this means that the potential energy of the photons forming the gas is no longer negligible, when compared with their kinetic energy: it corresponds to a real as opposed to an ideal

Fig. 1. Experimental demonstration of modal distribution inversion as the input beam power increases from a weakly nonlinear to highly nonlinear regime (dense photon gas). Top panels show the recorded near field images of the fiber output (left) and their reconstructions (right) according to the histogram (bottom).

photon gas. This case has been recently experimentally probed by Kirsch et al., who studied a Joule–Thomson type of expansion in a waveguide array optical system [5].

In this work, we demonstrate a novel property of these dense photon gases: the spontaneous transition from positive to negative absolute temperatures. To emphasize effects due to the non-ideal nature of a photon gas, the most favorable setup is provided by a few-mode optical fiber, where the potential energy can be greatly enhanced, thanks to the reduced volume that is accessible to the gas. By increasing the input beam power (or number of photons), we observed that the absolute temperature of the gas flips sign, leading to the inversion of mode power distribution. At low powers (in the ideal gas regime) the beam is dominated by the fundamental mode of the fiber; at high powers (in the real gas regime) the beam is dominated by the highest-order mode.

In experiments, we used a standard step-index optical fiber that supports the propagation of five modes at the selected wavelength of our femtosecond pump. A pulsed laser beam was injected into the center of the fiber core to optimize coupling into the fundamental mode. The measured near-field profiles of fiber output at different pump power levels are presented in Fig. 1. In linear propagation conditions, at peak powers on the order of 10 kW, the fiber output has a bell-shaped intensity profile, clearly dominated by the fundamental mode (Fig. 1a). As the power increases, the power is transferred from the fundamental to the higher-order modes, resulting in a speckled beam (Fig. 1b). In a highly nonlinear regime, i.e., for peak powers on the order of 100 kW, the fiber output is dominated by the highest-order guided mode LP₂₁ (Fig. 1c).

We determined the mode distributions at the fiber output by means of a holographic mode decomposition method [6]. In each case, the mode distributions are described by a Rayleigh-Jeans law, allowing for determining the values of the optical temperature T . As can be seen, as the beam power increases, the optical temperature flips its sign. In the weakly nonlinear regime, the highest population of the fundamental mode is associated with a positive optical temperature, $T > 0$. When a critical power value is reached, the measured near-uniform distribution of power across all guided modes can be associated with an optical temperature that increases towards infinity. For even larger powers, we observe an inversion of the input modal distribution, and the highest-order modes hold nearly 90% of the total power. This means that the absolute optical temperature is now negative, $T < 0$.

In conclusion, we have revealed that increasing the power of the laser beam propagating in a few-mode optical fiber results in a mode population redistribution, exhibiting a spontaneous inversion from the fundamental to the highest-order mode. This effect can be associated with a change from positive to negative absolute optical temperatures. Our results may have an important impact on the design and operation of multimode optical fiber systems and devices.

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References

1. F. O. Wu, A. U. Hassan, and D. N. Christodoulides, “Thermodynamic theory of highly multimoded nonlinear optical systems,” *Nat. Photonics* **13**, 776–782 (2019).
2. K. Baudin, J. Garnier, A. Fusaro, N. Berti, C. Michel, K. Krupa, G. Millot, and A. Picozzi, “Observation of light thermalization to negative-temperature Rayleigh-Jeans equilibrium states in multimode optical fibers,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **130**, 063801 (2023).
3. A. L. M. Muniz, F. O. Wu, P. S. Jung, M. Khajavikhan, D. N. Christodoulides, and U. Peschel, “Observation of photon-photon thermodynamic processes under negative optical temperature conditions,” *Science* **379**, 1019–1023 (2023).
4. M. Ferraro, F. Mangini, M. Zitelli, and S. Wabnitz, “On spatial beam self-cleaning from the perspective of optical wave thermalization in multimode graded-index fibers,” *Adv. Physics: X* **8**, 2228018 (2023).
5. M. S. Kirsch, G. G. Pyrialakos, R. Altenkirch, M. A. Selim, J. Beck, T. A. Wolterink, H. Ren, P. S. Jung, M. Khajavikhan, A. Szameit *et al.*, “Observation of Joule–Thomson photon-gas expansion,” *Nat. Phys.* **21**, 214–220 (2025).
6. M. Gervaziev, I. Zhdanov, D. Kharenko, V. Gonta, V. Volosi, E. Podivilov, S. Babin, and S. Wabnitz, “Mode decomposition of multimode optical fiber beams by phase-only spatial light modulator,” *Laser Phys. Lett.* **18**, 015101 (2020).